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waste places, plantation gardens, roadside grassland, arable and fallow land and is used as folklore herb in alleviating abdominal discomforts mainly stomach ulceration. *L. lavandulifolia* is also known for its use as sedative, vermifuge, dermatosis and insecticidal properties. In this context, an experiment on acaricidal activities against red spider mite (RSM), *Oligonychus coffeae* Nietner (Acarina : Tetranychidae) was conducted at Physiology Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat, which revealed presence of rich toxic bioactive principles with acaricidal and ovicidal properties. The crude ethyl alcoholic extract caused 46.00% to 97.00% adult mortality at 72 hours after treatment (HAT) with LC_{50} value of 1585.26 ppm. While evaluating bio-efficacy of the chromatographic fractions with chloroform, toluene and methyl alcohol against the adult RSM, toluene fraction at 0.05% concentration showed the highest activity causing 100.00% mortality followed by chloroform and methyl alcohol recording 88.00% and 71.00 % at 72 HAT with LC_{50} values of 6.62, 37.27 and 43.45 ppm, respectively. In terms of hatching success, all the three fractions showed promising results, while chloroform being the most toxic (6.27 %) followed by toluene (10.26%) and methyl alcohol fractions (44.36 %) with LC_{50} value of 5.24, 2.14 and 3727.88 ppm, respectively.

AE-7

MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL RESISTANCE TRAITS OF MUSKMELON AGAINST FRUIT FLY (*BACTROCERA CUCURBITAE* (COQUILLET)) IN HOT ARID REGION OF RAJASTHAN

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Plants genotypes possess different morphological and biochemical properties, which resultantly induce in them different mechanisms of resistance. Various antixenotic traits including length of pubescence, fruit toughness, rind thickness, flesh thickness, days to first harvest and fruit diameter, and alleochemical traits including flavinoid content, tannins content, phenols content, total alkaloids, pH and TSS total of fruit were studied on eleven genotypes of muskmelon (*Cucumis melo* L.) in relation to resistance against *B. cucurbitae* under field conditions in hot arid region of India. The significant differences were found in tested genotypes for fruit infestation and larval density/ fruit. AHMM/BR-1, RM-50 and AHMM/BR-8 were the most resistant; MHY-5, Durgapura Madhu and Pusa Sarabati were moderately resistant; AHMM/BR-13, Pusa Madhuras and Arka Jeet were susceptible whereas Arka Rajhans and GMM-3 were the highly susceptible genotypes to fruit fly in the season's viz., 2011 and 2012. The larval density per fruit increased with an increase in percentage fruit infestation and there was a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.97$) between per cent fruit infestation and larval density per fruit. Fruit diameter and days to first harvest had significant positive correlations whereas fruit toughness, rind thickness, flesh thickness

and length of ovary pubescence had significant negative correlations with the percent fruit infestation and larval density. Maximum variation in fruit infestation and larval density was explained by length of ovary pubescence (63.3 and 45.7% respectively) followed by fruit toughness (6.7 and 13.7% respectively) and fruit diameter (8.6 and 10.5% respectively). Total soluble solid and pH were lowest in resistant and highest in susceptible genotypes whereas tannins, phenols, alkaloids and flavinoid contents were highest in resistant and lowest in susceptible genotypes. Flavinoid and tannin contents explained (96.4 & 88.7 % respectively) of the total variation in fruit fly infestation and in larval density per fruit.

AE-8

STATUS OF *BEMISIA TABACI* (GENNADIUS) IN CONTEXT OF ECOLOGY AND ITS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN COTTON AGROECOSYSTEM

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Cotton is an important cash crop and extensively cultivated in different parts of the world. Many factors are responsible for its low productivity and production but the magnitude of insect-pests that damage the cotton crop from sowing to maturity, is most important. With the introduction of Bt cotton, bollworms are now not a problem but due to reduction of broad spectrum insecticides in Bt cotton, sucking insect-pests such as whitefly, mealy bug, jassid and aphid are playing havoc with the cotton crop (Xu *et al.*, 2008). Among these insect-pests, cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) is most serious pest of cotton. At present, it is globally distributed and is known to infest more than 600 plant species (Stansly and Naranjo, 2010). It causes damage to cotton crop by direct feeding and contamination of lint by honey dew and sooty mould. It also acts as vector of more than 100 plant viruses. In cotton, it transmits a deadly cotton leaf curl virus (Jones, 2003). *B. tabaci* has strong relationship with abiotic factors like temperature, humidity and precipitation. Temperature has positive correlation and relative humidity has negative correlation with whitefly. A combination of temperature (27°C) and relative humidity (71%) is highly important for its multiplication on cotton (Singh and Butter, 1985). For a multi-voltine and multi-crop pest like *B. tabaci* estimating rates of mortality in the field is extremely complex and difficult. So, life table studies are important to predict pest outbreaks and to develop pest management strategies (Naranjo and Ellsworth, 2005). Integrated pest management for whitefly has been successfully implemented in several cotton growing countries in the world. Such methods include host plant resistance, cultural control, biological control, use of botanicals, insect growth regulators and chemical insecticides (Stansly and Naranjo, 2010).